

Table 1. Donors of brown spot resistance in the Punjab, 1980 kharif.

IET No.	Designation	Source	Disease score ^a
7366	RNRO 1429	T. Hamsa/ Rasi	1
7367	RNR 27033	(T712/TNI)//HR 35	1
7343	KAU 23372	MN 54-42 mutant	3
7349	Co 32-20-66	-	3
7353	TNAU 13932/2	-	3
7364	RNRO 1446	T. Hamsa/ Rasi	3
7368	RNR 36718	(GEB 24/Sigadis)//(IR8/RNR 8102)	3
7417	R243-3041	IR7516(IR2071-625-1-252/205-3-521-3-3)	3
7497	CR294-28-1	(IR20/Zenith)// Malagkit Sungsong	3
7513	HPU5048-Pep 9-1B	JC 98/Kulu	3
7547	RP1442-2-2-3-5	Rasi/ K 46-15-B ₂	3
7145	CR263-889	T 141/Baok/T 141	3
6978	CR141-5036 CRRP5	(N22/TN1)//(T90/IR8)	3
7261	RP897-3790-30-1	Rasi/Mettasanna	3
6151	CR141-60-58-2-295	(N22/TNI)//(T90/IRS)	3
6686	IR42 (IR2071-586-5-6)	IR2042/CR 94-13	3
7291	PY 1	Ponni/IR8	3
-	Susceptible check7		

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9.

Table 2. Distribution of scores of resistance donors of brown spot of rice at PAU Rice Research Sub-Station, Gurdaspur, Punjab.

Score ^a	Leaf area infected	Resistance donors	
		Number	Percent
1	Less than 1%	2	0.35
3	1-5%	15	2.63
5	5-25%	467	81.93
7	25-50%	79	13.86
9	More than 50%	7	1.22

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

entries were scored resistant; 15 were moderately resistant (Table 1). The distribution of scores is in Table 2. The resistant and moderately resistant donors are being used in Punjab breeding programs. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Gall midge infestation in a monthly-planted trial

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A 10-m² plot of BG34-8 rice variety was transplanted on the first of each calendar month beginning in March 1977 and ending in February 1979 at Batalagoda. Infestation of gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* was assessed by counting the infested hills in the total area planted at 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting. After each count the galls were removed to avoid subsequent recounting.

The total number of hills sampled and the total infested hills at 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting were used to calculate the percentage of gall midge infestation for 3 particular planting dates. Gall midge infestation was bimodal with a major peak in the December planting and a minor peak in the June planting. Furthermore, data on the mean rainfall for the 2 years show that the infestations peaked 2 months after the peak rainfall (see figure). These findings are being used to plan field screening tests such as the International Rice Gall Midge Nursery and the Gall Midge Biotype study. ■

Gall midge infestation and rainfall at Central Rice Breeding Station, Sri Lanka.

Chemical differences in rice varieties susceptible or resistant to gall midge and stem borer

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Gall midge *Orseolia (Pachydiplosis) oryzae* and yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* are two major internal feeder

pests of rice. Varietal differences in resistance to these pests have long been observed. To understand the mechanism of resistance, we undertook biochemical studies of selected resistant and susceptible varieties.

Because the gall midge attacks the vegetative shoot apex and the stem borer attacks the stem, 1-cm-long vegetative shoot apices and 2.54-cm-long